

CHLORINE-DOPED GRAPHENE OXIDE/POLY (VINYLIDENE FLUORIDE) NANOCOMPOSITES: EXCEPTIONAL DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports our recent work [1] on developing a facile and controllable method to fabricate chlorinated reduced graphene oxide (Cl-rGO)/poly (vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) composites with exceptional dielectric constants and low loss tangents. The observed results are explained in terms of the modifications in structure, elemental composition, electrical conductivity, Cl-rGO/PVDF interfacial interaction and PVDF phase transformation. GO sheets are doped with chlorine by mixing thionyl chloride into the GO dispersion, resulting in the formation of both charge transfer complexes and covalently bonded chlorine on GO sheets. Cl functions as an electron acceptor, i.e. p-type dopant, and an optimal chlorination gives rise to a maximum ionic Cl along with the highest charge carrier density of GO and the highest electrical conductivity of the composites. Strong interfacial interactions exist between the Cl-rGO sheets and PVDF chains due to chlorination, allowing the adsorption of F atoms onto the basal plane of GO sheets to form β -phase PVDF, to the benefit of enhanced dielectric constants of the composites. The Cl-rGO/PVDF composites with 0.2-0.4 vol% graphene present high dielectric constants and moderate loss tangents: e.g. a dielectric constant of 364 – equivalent to 13 times that of the neat PVDF – with a moderately increased loss tangent of 0.077 at 1 kHz with 0.2 vol% graphene. These values are among the best dielectric performance ever reported to date for composites containing graphene, CNTs and other carbon fillers. The synergy stemming from chlorination of GO sheets on the dielectric properties of Cl-rGO/PVDF are identified. Materials with high dielectric constants are broadly employed in electronics and electromechanical systems, such as embedded capacitors in microelectronics, electromagnetic interference shielding and energy-storage devices.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer-matrix composites with high dielectric constants and low losses are extensively employed in electronics and electromechanical systems due to their easy processing, flexibility and high dielectric breakdown strengths. Several different methods have been studied to develop polymer composites possessing excellent dielectric performance: namely, (i) selection of proper polymer matrices; (ii) addition of ceramic additives with high dielectric constants; (iii) incorporation of conductive organics, such as polymers or oligomers; and (iv) addition of inorganic conductive reinforcement [2-4]. Among the above, incorporation of conductive carbon fillers, such as carbon nanotubes and graphene, is

considered most promising and widely studied recently.

To explain the dielectric properties of composites with conductive fillers, the Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars polarization principle is employed: the charges are entrapped between the interfaces of different phases with different electrical conductivities [5]. It follows then that fillers having high charge carrier concentrations and high electrical conductivities are beneficial to enhancing the dielectric constants of composites. Reduced graphene oxide (rGO) has been widely used to reinforce polymer composites [6-7]. Chemical doping further increases the electrical conductivity of rGO sheets by introducing extra charge carriers [8, 9], thus increasing the dielectric constants of the composites made therefrom. Among different doping agents, a chemical treatment by thionyl chloride (SOCl_2) is one of the most efficient choices [10, 11]. The charge-transfer complexes formed on graphene is responsible for the improved electrical conductivity. Chlorinated rGO (Cl-rGO) sheets were found stable in solvents, like N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) [12], due to the enhanced repulsive forces between them with absorbed Cl ions. Therefore, chlorination of CNTs and graphene have been widely studied, but their use in composite fabrication is uncommon.

This work is dedicated to developing chlorine-doped GO (Cl-GO)/polymer composites with high dielectric constants and low losses by treating GO dispersions with SOCl_2 (Figure 1). The process employed here is sonication-free, allowing us to maintain large-size GO sheets to the benefit of enhanced dielectric constants. The nature of C-Cl bonds is evaluated to relate to the charge carrier densities and the electrical conductivities of Cl-GO. Excellent dielectric performance of the Cl-rGO/PVDF composites with β -phase PVDF matrix is revealed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Composites synthesis

GO was prepared using the modified Hummers method [13]. The dispersion with polydispersed GO sheets was classified to collect large-size GO dispersion after centrifugation. The GO dispersion was centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 40 min to divide into supernatant and precipitate. The precipitate was collected and diluted to 1 mg/mL using DMF and ultrasonicated for 15 min using a bath sonicator.

SOCl_2 was mixed into the GO dispersion in the ratio of $\text{SOCl}_2:\text{GO} = 1:10$ in volume, which was stirred for 5 min before heating to 70 °C for up to 6 h. The chlorinated GO (Cl-GO) was added to DMF-diluted PVDF (Kynar, 1.78 g/cm³ in density) solution and stirred for 1 h. The mixture was casted and cured at 80 °C for 24 h, which was reduced by hydrazine vapor at 95 °C for 2h. The composite was post-cured at 170 °C for 6 h to obtain mildly reduced fillers (labeled as Cl-rGO). The Cl-rGO/PVDF composites were compressed at 200 °C for 30 min at 100 MPa to form ~15 mm thick composite plates. The flowchart for the preparation of Cl-rGO/PVDF composites is illustrated in Figure 1. Neat PVDF and GO/PVDF composites were also prepared using the same procedure. The filler volume fractions in the composites were estimated using the density of both rGO and Cl-rGO as 2.2 g/cm³ [14].

Figure 1: Simplified flowchart for the preparation of Cl-rGO/PVDF composites.

2.2 Characterization

The size distribution of GO was obtained by analyzing the SEM images using the software ImageJ [15]. Raman spectroscopy (Reinshaw MicroRman System) was used to evaluate the structure of GO sheets. The electrical conductivities and charge carrier concentrations of GO before and after chlorination were measured using the four-point probe method on a resistivity/Hall measurement system (Bio-Rad HL5500PC). The nature of C-Cl bonds and interaction between SOCl_2 and GO were studied by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, Axis Ultra DLD). The functional groups on the GO basal plane after chlorination and the interfacial interaction between the chlorinated fillers and the PVDF matrix were studied by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR, Bruker Vertex 70 Hyperion 1000). The phase compositions of the PVDF matrices were examined by X-ray diffraction (XRD, PANalytical X'pert Pro) using $\text{Cu K}\alpha 1$ ($\lambda = 0.154 \text{ nm}$) radiation. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, Setaram 90/39324) was used to study the crystallization of the neat PVDF and composites. The crystallinities X_c were calculated according to [16]:

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_m^0 \cdot \omega} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_m is the melting enthalpy during heating, ΔH_m^0 is the melting enthalpy of 100% crystalline pure PVDF (104.7 J/g) [16], and ω is the mass percentage of PVDF in the composites. The dielectric properties of the composites were measured using an impedance/gain-phase analyzer (Hewlett Packard 4149A) in the frequencies ranging from 100 Hz to 40 MHz.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Nature of C-Cl bonds and electrical conductivities of chlorinated GO

Large-size monolayer GO sheets with an average area of $477 \mu\text{m}^2$, as seen in Figure 2a, was employed to make composites. The Raman spectra given in Figure 2b present two bands for both GO and Cl-GO: the D-band at $\sim 1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ represents disordered sp^3 structure while the G-band at $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to the first-order scattering of the E_{2g} mode [17]. The G-band position of GO shifts to higher frequencies after p-doping, while to lower frequencies after n-doping because of the formation of different types of charge-transfer complexes [10]. The degree of shift using the same doping method is a reflection of the extent of doping: a more significant doping effect corresponds to a higher charge carrier concentration, and thus a larger shift [9, 18]. According to Figure 2b, the G-band of Cl-GO shifted from 1595 cm^{-1} to 1605 cm^{-1} with a 2 h SOCl_2 treatment, suggesting the most effective p-type doping. The electrical conductivities and charge carrier concentrations of GO increased after chlorination, as

shown in Figure 2c. After the SOCl_2 treatment, both the covalent and ionic Cl formed on the basal plane of GO sheets [11, 12]. The ionic Cl created charge-transfer complexes and acted as electron acceptors, which in turn increased the charge carrier concentration [12]. It is noted that both the electrical conductivity and charge carrier concentration of Cl-GO underwent three orders of magnitude improvements and reached the highest value after 2 h chlorination. The dielectric properties of polymer-matrix composites are strongly related to the intrinsic electrical conductivities of fillers. Therefore, Cl-rGO sheets obtained with 2 h chlorination were chosen for the fabrication of PVDF-based composites.

Figure 2: (a) Size distribution of GO and a typical SEM image in inset (scale bar: 10 μm); (b) Raman spectra of Cl-GO with different degrees of chlorination and the corresponding G-band shifts in inset; and (c) electrical conductivity and charge carrier density of Cl-GO as a function of chlorination duration.

The elemental compositions of Cl-GO with different chlorination durations were analyzed using XPS, as shown in Table 1. The atomic ratio of Cl to S varied depending on chlorination duration, but consistently maintained higher than that in SOCl_2 molecules, confirming chemical reactions between GO and SOCl_2 .

Chlorination duration	Elements (at%)				
	O	C	Cl	S	Cl/S ratio
0	29.9	70.1	-	-	-
1 h	21.3	72.3	4.5	1.9	2.4
2 h	21.9	70.3	5.6	2.2	2.5
3 h	22.5	73.4	3.1	1.0	3.1
4 h	22.2	73.9	3.1	0.8	4.0
5 h	20.3	75.4	3.4	0.9	3.8
6 h	21.9	74.1	3.1	0.9	3.5

Table 1: Summary of elemental compositions of GO with different chlorination durations.

Figure 3a shows the general XPS spectra of GO before and after the SOCl_2 treatment. The Cl and S

peaks appeared after chlorination, suggesting successful doping. The deconvoluted C 1s peaks for both GO and Cl-GO (Figure 3b) presented C=C/C-C (284.5 eV), C-O (epoxy/hydroxyl, 286.5 eV), C=O (carbonyl, 287.8 eV) and COOH (carboxyl, 288.9 eV) groups [19-21]. A new peak for the C-S (286.1 eV) bonds appeared in Cl-GO, indicating the existence of -C-S-C- bonds due to the covalent crosslinking between the GO sheets [22]. In addition, the peak intensities of C-O and C-OOH groups in Cl-GO diminished compared to those in GO sheets, which explains the nucleophilic substitution between chloride and -OH/-COOH groups [22]. The Cl 2p core level spectrum revealed two nonequivalent chlorine sites from the 3/2 and 1/2 levels, which are separated by 1.4 eV due to spin-orbit coupling. The doublet located at a lower binding energy corresponds to charge-transfer complexes formed between ionic chlorine and GO; while the doublet at a higher binding energy implies covalent C-Cl bonds [12, 23]. The deconvolution of S 2p spectra revealed the formation of C-S bonds and SO₄²⁻ groups [22].

Figure 3: XPS spectra of GO obtained before and after chlorination: (a) general XPS spectra of GO with different chlorination durations; (b) deconvoluted spectra of C 1s of GO and Cl-GO after chlorination for 2 h; deconvoluted XPS curve fittings of (c) Cl 2p and (d) S 2p.

The atomic concentration of Cl and the fraction of its ionic and covalent states are shown in Figure 4. As the chlorination duration increased, the atomic concentration of Cl initially increased significantly reaching to a maximum of ~5.5 at% at 2 h, and reduced to a constant value. The fraction of ionic Cl (two blue peaks in Figure 3c) showed a similar trend with a maximum at 2 h, which is consistent with the highest electrical conductivity (Figure 2c). The equilibrium between the chemical reaction and the physical adsorption can explain the above phenomenon. For durations below 2 h, both the chemical reaction and the physical adsorption took place rapidly once the SOCl₂ molecules were in contact with GO sheets because of the sufficient doping/reactive sites [22]. This resulted in a large rise of Cl atomic concentrations. When the available doping/reactive sites were occupied, a further treatment resulted in a large reduction in Cl atomic concentration due to the desorption of Cl with an associated balance between the covalent- and ionic-Cl [24].

Figure 4: Atomic concentration of Cl in GO, and fractions of Cl in ionic and covalent states as a function of chlorination duration. (Solid line is only a guide to the eyes for atomic concentration of Cl).

3.2 Interfacial interaction and phase composition

FT-IR was used to study the interactions between GO sheets and SOCl_2 , as shown in Figure 5a. After the SOCl_2 treatment, a new peak at $\sim 710 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to C-Cl bonds appeared, confirming the successful chlorine doping of GO. The interfacial interactions in GO/PVDF and Cl-rGO/PVDF are shown in Figure 5b. The broad peaks at $\sim 3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ represent the stretching vibration of O-H bonds. Compared to rGO/PVDF, the O-H peak of Cl-rGO/PVDF downshifted from 3415 cm^{-1} to 3402 cm^{-1} (inset 2 in Figure 5b), indicating stronger hydrogen bonds in the latter composites [25]. The peak at $\sim 870 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to $>\text{CF}_2$ and the skeletal bending vibration upshifted from 871 cm^{-1} to 874 cm^{-1} (inset 1 in Figure 5b), because of the strong dipolar interaction between the $>\text{CF}_2$ groups in PVDF chains and the newly formed $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups in chlorinated rGO sheets [26, 27].

Figure 5: FT-IR spectra of (a) GO before and after chlorination; and (b) rGO/PVDF and Cl-rGO/PVDF composites with 0.4 vol% filler content.

Figure 6a shows the XRD spectra of pristine GO, rGO/PVDF and Cl-rGO/PVDF composites, along with their crystallinity in the inset. The peak of pristine GO at 10.33° disappeared in rGO/PVDF and Cl-rGO/PVDF composites because of the uniform dispersion of rGO and Cl-rGO sheets in the PVDF matrix. The rGO/PVDF composite had characteristic peaks, α (100), α/γ (020), α/γ (110) and α (021)/ γ (022) at diffraction angles $2\theta = 17.66, 18.30, 20.04, 26.56^\circ$, respectively, as well as small peaks of β (200)/(110) and β (310) at $2\theta = 20.7$ and 36.3° . All these peaks suggest a predominant α/γ phase together with a small fraction of β -phase. In the Cl-rGO/PVDF composite, the peaks β (200)/(110) and β (310) were intensified significantly because the enhanced interfacial interactions between Cl-rGO and PVDF

resulted in additional F atoms absorbed in the Cl-rGO planes, causing the modification of chain conformation of the PVDF matrix at the interfacial region from TGTG' (α -PVDF) to all trans conformation (β -PVDF). The crystallinity of Cl-rGO/PVDF composites increased with increasing filler content, and the crystallinity was higher in Cl-rGO/PVDF than rGO/PVDF. It is seen that the chlorination of rGO enhanced the nucleation effect of rGO sheets for PVDF chains.

Figure 6: (a) XRD spectra of pristine GO, rGO/PVDF, and Cl-rGO/PVDF composites, as well as crystallinity of composites with different filler contents in inset; and (b) schematic views of TGTG' (α -phase) and TTTT type chains (β -phase) of PVDF.

3.3 Dielectric properties

The electrical and dielectric properties of PVDF composites are shown in Figure 7. The AC conductivities of Cl-rGO/PVDF composites enhanced with increasing filler content, and there was a percolation threshold at the filler content near 0.32 vol%. The dielectric constants of the Cl-rGO/PVDF composites significantly improved with moderate increases in loss tangent as the filler content increased (Figures 7b and 7c). The Cl-rGO/PVDF composite with 0.2 vol% graphene delivered a remarkable dielectric constant of 364 at 1 kHz, which was 78% and 13 times higher than those of the rGO/PVDF composite and the neat PVDF, respectively. The corresponding loss tangent values of the three materials were 0.077, 0.088 and 0.0029, respectively. These dielectric properties obtained at 1 kHz are summarized in Fig. 7d where the performance between the two composites can be clearly distinguished. Both the dielectric constants and the losses of rGO/PVDF remained very low regardless of the filler content because of the relatively low electrical conductivity of the filler. In contrary, the dielectric constants of the Cl-rGO/PVDF composites enhanced greatly at the expense of initially moderate and later large increases in dielectric loss.

As a brief summary, the exceptional dielectric properties of the Cl-rGO/PVDF composites in this study are attributed to several factors: (i) the significantly enhanced electrical conductivity of Cl-rGO due to the p-doping effect of chlorine; (ii) the transformation from the dominating α -phase into the β -phase of PVDF matrix; (iii) the enhanced Cl-rGO/PVDF interfacial interactions and (iv) the high permanent dipole moment and high polarizability of C-Cl bonds.

Figure 7: Electrical conductivities and dielectric properties of rGO/PVDF and Cl-rGO/PVDF nanocomposites containing different filler contents: (a) AC conductivity; (b) dielectric constant; (c) dielectric loss with the inset plotted on a linear scale; and (d) dielectric properties at 1 kHz of composites with different filler contents.

The dielectric properties of the current Cl-rGO/PVDF composites are compared with those reported in the literature for composites containing CNTs or rGO as reinforcement [28-33]. In general, both dielectric constant and loss increase with increasing filler content, as shown in Figure 8. It can be said that the composites fabricated in this study achieved much higher dielectric constants than the others for a given dielectric loss. This finding makes the Cl-rGO/PVDF composite ideally suited for high-k and low-loss applications, such as energy storage and embedded capacitors.

Figure 8: Comparison of dielectric properties of polymer-matrix composites with CNTs or rGO as reinforcement, showing the relationship between dielectric constant and loss. In the brackets are the ranges of volume fractions of fillers reported in the references. The arrow in the top indicates the direction of increasing filler content.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We report a novel and facile method to fabricate the chlorinated GO by direct addition of SOCl_2 into

the GO dispersion and exceptional dielectric properties are obtained for Cl-rGO/PVDF composites. The modifications in structure, elemental composition, electrical conductivity, Cl-rGO/PVDF interfacial interaction and PVDF phase transformation were evaluated to account for the enhanced dielectric performance. A summary of made in the following.

- (i) Both the ionic and covalent C-Cl bonds were formed on the basal plane of GO after the SOCl₂ treatment. The ionic Cl created charge-transfer complexes with GO sheets, resulting in p-type doping. 2 h chlorination duration gave the best p-type doping effect of GO, which was accompanied by the highest charge carrier density, the best electrical conductivity and the maximum upshift of G band.
- (ii) Enhance interfacial interactions between the Cl-rGO sheets and PVDF polymer chains were identified arising from the strong hydrogen bonds between O-H (in Cl-rGO) and F (in PVDF matrix), and newly formed dipolar interaction between C=O and F. This allowed the adsorption of F atoms onto the basal plane of GO sheets, leading to the formation of β -polymorph.
- (iii) The exceptional dielectric properties of the Cl-rGO/PVDF composites are attributed to several factors, such as the greatly increased electrical conductivity and the C-Cl bonds with high polarity and polarizability of Cl-rGO, as well as the improved interfacial interaction and the large percentage of β -PVDF in Cl-rGO/PVDF composites.

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